

Ultra-Low Latency 5G CHARISMA Architecture for Secure Intelligent Transportation Verticals

M.C. Parker*, Senior Member, IEEE, G. Koczian, S.D. Walker

University of Essex, Wivenhoe, Essex, CO4 3SQ, UK, e-mail: mcpark@essex.ac.uk

K. Habel, V. Jungnickel, Fraunhofer HHI, Berlin, DE; Th. Rokkas, I. Neokosmidis, INCITES, Luxembourg,

M.S. Siddiqui, E. Escalona, I2CAT Fundació, Barcelona, Spain

C. Canales-Valenzuela, Ericsson, Vía Poblados 13, 28040 Madrid, Spain

A. Foglar, M. Ulbricht, Innoroute GmbH, Munich, DE; Y. Liu, J.C. Point, JCP-Connect, Rennes, France

D. Kritharidis, K.V. Katsaros, Intracom Telecom, 19.7 Km Markopoulou, Ave., 190 02 Peania, Greece

E. Trouva, Y. Angelopoulos, Inst. of Informatics & Telecommunications, NCSRDI, Athens, Greece

K. Filis, G. Lyberopoulos, COSMOTE Mobile Communications S.A., Athens, Greece

E. Zetserov, D. Levi, Ethernity Networks Ltd., Lod, Israel; P. Kralj, P. Jenko, Telekom Solvenia, Ljubljana

ABSTRACT

We describe low end-to-end latencies of 6.69 ms in the 5G CHARISMA network, that has been optimised for both device and system technologies speed, as well as with its virtualised, hierarchical and distributed, edge-centric architecture, that processes data as near as possible to their source and destination. Such an ultra-high speed 5G network can be utilised in intelligent transport system (ITS) applications, and we describe a public transport bus-based use case that takes advantage of the CHARISMA capabilities.

Keywords: 5G converged network, low latency, mobile edge computing, virtualised security, transportation.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the key drivers pushing forward the development of 5G technologies is the emergence of intelligent transportation systems (ITS) suitable for road and rail applications, which particularly rely on ultra-low latency, high-speed, ultra-high reliable and secure digital connectivity. 5G key performance indicators (KPIs) have been defined [1] targeting 5 ms end-to-end latency times, and 10 ms instantiation times. A key objective of the 5G-PPP CHARISMA [2] project is to create an ultra-low latency 5G technical solution suitable for future ITS applications, and here we report on the latest experimental and architecture embodiment.

2. ULTRA-LOW LATENCY ARCHITECTURE

CHARISMA adopts a distributed control, management & orchestration (CMO) architecture, bringing intelligence as close to the edge as possible, to reduce latency times and provide a finer resolution control of the 5G network resources using SDN and NFV capabilities. CHARISMA features a hierarchical architecture, placing intelligence nodes at points where aggregation of access, backhaul and core networks occurs: Converged Aggregation Levels (CALs). Each CAL intelligence node contains an Intelligence Management Unit (IMU) containing computing, storage and networking resources, in which network functions can be deployed by the CMO to maintain efficient and low-latency operation. Virtual network functions (VNFs) can be chosen not to be instantiated at each CAL node of the CHARISMA hierarchy. Fig.1 indicates the Virtualization Plane above the PHY infrastructure layer, where the component elements of the IMU present at each CAL are realised. Each of the IMUs above the CAL2, CAL1, and CAL0 are cloudlets of the overall CHARISMA CMO, such that the CAL3 (central office) does not have to have an IMU cloudlet directly associated with it; rather, CAL3 may be associated with the main cloud infrastructure (e.g. data centre, DC) where the overall “centralised” M&O system

Fig.1 CHARISMA integrated PHY, virtualized infrastructure, and CMO planes

Fig.2 Bus use case scenario mapped to CHARISMA PHY architecture

is located. The Control Plane above the virtualised infrastructure layer represents the CMO comprising the controller entities for the management and orchestration of the physical and virtual CHARISMA resources. With the CMO moderately centralised in a DC close to the CAL3 (i.e. the CO), certain functions or “CMO agents” are therefore also distributed in multiple micro-DCs (μ DCs) closer to the network edge. Distributed functions enable intelligence closer to the network edge, gathering and initial processing of data on the 5G network and the road/rail transport operation as required, enabling rapid response times, and a more local, precise security policy.

3. ULTRA-LOW LATENCY 5G TECHNOLOGIES

A bus-based public transport use case [3] represents the CHARISMA low latency features, as well as demonstrate other important 5G KPIs such as network isolation/slicing and high data access throughput. Buses or trams operate along a regular route and a published transport timetable, so allowing provision of network services such as caching and routing for optimized Internet access, to reduce resources and service latency. Each bus is equipped with a wireless/mobile cache device (MoBcache, MB) at the CAL0 gateway that:

- accesses the Internet by connecting to a WiFi access point located at the bus stop through the radio or WiFi network, or connecting to an eNodeB BS (CAL2) either through a LTE network or a similar to 5G;
- enables caching functionality and provides content to end users through local caches.

At the bus stops (CAL1), a WiFi AP with cache functionality is deployed to provide Internet connections for passing buses. The MBs either connect to the AP through WiFi when the bus is approaching the bus stop, or switch to eNodeB through LTE when WiFi services are not available. Traffic is offloaded between WiFi and mobile (LTE/5G) networks to provide seamless handover and service continuity. The MBs deployed on different buses automatically create an ad-hoc network (“mobile CDN”), which ensures continuous use of content even when disconnected. The 5G features that the CHARISMA architecture has been designed to support are:

1) Low latency

There are two aspects to low latency: i) end-to-end latency, e.g. for live video; and ii) access time. For the first of these, a traveller on the bus is watching, e.g. a streamed live football match. The ultra-low latency aspects of the CHARISMA architecture (i.e. accelerated NIC cards, and TrustNode routing) act together to ensure an as-low-as-possible delay for the streamed video. CHARISMA’s hierarchical architecture fosters low latency since the network structures simplify the output port determination process in the CAL nodes, speeding up propagation delay inside devices [4], e.g. the hardware routing platform *TrustNode*. If the traveller changes buses at an intermediate location, the lowest common CAL point (e.g. CAL2) co-ordinates handover from the CAL0 of the bus to the bus stop CAL1, enabling a seamless video experience. For the low access time, if the traveller wants to watch a different video, the hierarchical caching system transfers and locates popular videos at the lowest video cache storage locations, and knows the traveller’s use profile and preferences, so as to transfer content in advance to CAL IMU caches nearest to the traveller, in anticipation of exercising preferences.

2) Seamless connectivity:

There are various aspects to the seamless connectivity that the automotive use case demonstrates. E.g., a passenger on a journey is watching a streamed video on his mobile device (tablet, smartphone etc.). After requesting the video, the data for the video is downloaded and cached locally at the CAL0 of the bus gateway. The traveller changes bus at an intermediate point. When the bus arrives, the traveller descends from the bus (while still watching the video) and the video caching source is transferred from the CAL0 of the bus, to the bus stop CAL1 cache. This is managed and controlled by the CAL2 node, the lowest common aggregation level. Without the traveller noticing any interruption, the video continues to stream at the bus stop while he is directly connected to the CAL1 micro-BS and its own local cache. When the connecting bus arrives, he gets into the bus, and his device automatically connects to the CAL0 gateway of the new bus, where the video is downloaded to the cache located at the CAL0 IMU, and he continues to watch the video without interruption. This seamless handover is co-ordinated by the same CAL2 node as the previous handover.

3) Enhanced Security

a) In-Bus communications: The CHARISMA in-bus networking infrastructure can be used as part of the in-bus monitoring and control system for the bus driver, e.g. to monitor status of individual compartments (e.g. upstairs and downstairs for double decker buses), exit and entrance doors, integrity of bus windows and CCTV cameras etc. Such an in-bus signalling network needs safeguarding against intrusion, hijacking, data corruption (including jamming, interceptions, and spoofing), and DoS;

b) Bus-to-Bus Station Control Centre (e.g. CAL2): There are 2 aspects to the control signalling here:

i) Communications with bus controllers at the bus station, and with other bus drivers (e.g. different buses traveling along same route, or in the vicinity). Here, the integrity and reliability of the communications between bus controllers and other bus drivers mean low-latency is critical for time-critical signaling, and safety alerts;

ii) Data (internet) communications between bus and base-stations - this relates to the use by bus passengers of bus-to-street communications links for their own private data consumption requirements such that the link needs to be secure against intrusion, hijacking, data corruption (inc. jamming, interceptions, spoofing), and DoS etc.

The proposed physical layer (PHY) architecture described in this section has been successfully set up and tested. Fig.2 shows the schematic diagram of the test bed and how it maps onto the bus use case. CAL0 consists of a laptop that wirelessly connects to the mobile cache (MB on the bus) that has a Gigabit Ethernet connection to the 60GHz RF modem. The data is then sent over 60GHz (802.11ad) to the compatible docking station where the cache function is deployed at CAL1. The docking station connects to the TrustNode router at CAL2 that handles and accelerates the IPv6 traffic via Gigabit Ethernet. Through this process the data is routed to CAL3 that represents the Telco Cloud (and the Internet). The components of the low latency demonstrator and their various interactions are described as follows, starting at CAL3 and working down the hierarchy towards CAL0:

Server with hardware accelerated NIC: The server is equipped with a hardware accelerated NIC (also known as a SmartNIC), which has several physical connections. Configured by the server process, the SmartNIC automatically selects traffic, related to a specific Application and proceeds per flow packet editing instead of CPU Application, reducing CPU Load, drastically decreasing latency to almost sub 10µs This direct-processing of flows in programmable HW has high level forwarding prediction and is not delayed by CPU processing; important for time sensitive applications. SmartNIC has flexible API and Open Flow 1.4 agent for configuration.

TrustNode router: is a network element preferentially handling IPv6 traffic, with handling done in HW or SW:

- Hardware accelerated: IPv6 traffic with special prefix “AF” and 6Tree routing procedure [4]; Special flows specified using OpenFlow rule offloading.
- Software processed traffic: all other packets, using Open vSwitch.

Fig.3: CHARISMA logical experimental architecture

Fig.4: Schematic of CHARISMA experimental point-to-point latencies

Routing IPv6 traffic in hardware speeds up any introduced delay dramatically, in comparison to other IPv6 network elements. For fast-forwarding IPv6 packets, a special treelike address schema called 6Tree is needed, where the TrustNode is configured to process a predefined part of the network address. In this case, this is the first byte following the “AF” fast prefix. The value of this byte directly indicates the output-port of the processed packet. So, for example, all traffic with a destination address of “AF1” is directed to port 1 of the TrustNode, which is connected to the 60-GHz radio equipment. All traffic with the fast prefix “AF2” is directed to the layer1 cache (port 2). A second key feature of the device is an automatic OpenFlow offloading rule. Some flows in the flow table of the software OpenFlow switch running inside the device are transferred to the hardware acceleration layer. This offers the possibility to further reduce the delay in SDN-managed networks.

Level 1 (L1) Cache: The caching system consists of several levels of caches and a cache controller, which is located in the server. The caches store content that is often requested by users. The location and migration of the saved content is controlled by the cache controller, which follows a strategy to store requested content as near as possible to the end-user. Due to physical considerations, not every cache is able to store all the content, such that a hierarchical cache topology is therefore used.

Level 0 (L0) Cache: The layer L0 cache is also part of the hierarchically caching system.

Caches at the L0 level act additionally as wireless access points providing IEEE802.11 access to the users.

The link technologies and the intelligent nodes described below require the following specific software.

Cloud and Content Server:

The application server provides video content, while the content streamer sends video to network, and is activated upon network readiness. The solution uses the Linux OS as being the most suitable for a NFV/SDN environment. First of all, the cloud-content server runs DHCP Server, to provide an IP address to each device in network. We use the IPv6 address pool for data forwarding and IPv4 for control flow, so DHCP supports both. Another application running on the server is the cache-manager, responsible for configuring the cache solution at any network point. The third main component managed on the server is the NIC, responsible for both forwarding data to CPU (local content server) and to the Internet (i.e. Internet content server such as Youtube.) The NIC can be managed in different ways, but we have decided to use a CLI (e.g. SSH), which is activated upon in the demo, and includes forwarding from network to network, and colouring the content traffic to provide high priority.

MoBcache and Content Cache: This has following control features:

- A manager which controls the device connectivity and can configure the wireless mesh network;

A cache controller which interfaces with the network operator or OTT/content provider, and controls the caching and pre-fetching strategy in an SDN framework. Caching and pre-fetching strategies can be set in a D2D manner (managed by MoBcache) or network-to-device configurations (controlled by the cache controller).

4. SYSTEM/CACHING END-TO-END LATENCY

The CHARISMA experimental setup is shown in Fig.3, with tests performed on the Internet to end-users caching data solution, where content-data is allocated at the server at CAL3, and requested by end-user device. Resulting measured point-to-point latencies are shown in Fig.4 and tabulated in Table 1. Many of the individual link delays are well below 1 ms, in keeping to achieve an overall end-to-end latency of below 5 ms. This also includes the processing delay at the TrustNode of CAL1, and the internal delay to the cache box. However, the 60-GHz link has shown a higher latency of about 3 ms, due to bridging between Ethernet and wireless 802.11ad protocols. Table 2 compares the end-to-end service latency for the cases with and without caches in the network, when a HTTP Live Streaming video with quality of 3.4 Mbps is played. The 1st response is the latency between sending the user request and receiving the response from the content server or a cache. The start-up time is the latency between initial playlist request and start up of playback on the screen. The results show that improvement of service latency is significant by deploying caches in the network. The accelerated NIC card technology has been

Table 1: Tabulated target and expt. round trip latencies

Test	Description	Target time	Expt. round trip time
1	PC to Content server (end-to-end latency)	<5ms	6.69ms
2	PC to Content server	<0.5ms	3.12ms
3	PC to Cache box (L0)	<0.3ms	1.128ms
4	Cache box to TrustNode	<0.2ms	0.292ms
5	Cache box to content server	<0.2ms	0.541ms
6	Cache box to content server	<0.5ms	3.471ms
7	TrustNode to Cache box (L3)	<0.2ms	0.382ms
8	TrustNode to WiFi	<0.2ms	0.406ms
9	TrustNode to Content Server	<0.2ms	0.414ms
10	WiFi to Content Server	<0.2ms	0.415ms
11	SmartNIC Internet to Test Network with L3/L2 flow ¹	10μs	10μs
12	SmartNIC Internet to Test Network with SLA ¹	10μs	10μs

Table 2: Caching latency improvement

End-to-End service latency	W/O caches (ms)	With caches (ms)	Improve (ms)
1st response	17	13	4 (24%)
Start-up time	1,503	1,040	463 (33%)

Table 3: Node Latency improvement

Network element	Reference latency	Improved latency
TrustNode	165 μs ¹	2.5 μs ¹
SmartNIC	200μs-4ms ¹	<10μs

tested for Internet to Test Network acceleration with the expected results, i.e. Packet forwarding validated in comparison with standard CPU (by VNF) forwarding. CPU both L3/L2 and SLA processing takes in between 200μs to 2-4ms depends on CPU load. Table 3 shows how the hardware acceleration of the routing functionalities in the TrustNode device and the usage of the 6Tree latency optimized routing concept, has enabled a latency

improvement down to 1.5% of the originally value.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have described the 6.69-ms end-to-device latency of the 5G CHARISMA architecture employing an innovative, edge-centric architecture and ultra-low latency technology. We have identified the sources of the various latency components in the network, showing where the current delays are highest (i.e. in the 60-GHz links) to indicate prospects for reducing the latencies still further to below the 5-ms 5G-PPP KPI target. We have also outlined how the ultra-low latency, secure and open access CHARISMA architecture can find important application in future ITS situations, specifically in a public transport bus use case scenario.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This project has received funding from the EU's H2020 programme under grant agreement No. 671704.

REFERENCES

- [1] SRIA "Pervasive Mobile Virtual Services" of NetWorld 2020 ETP: http://www.networld2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2014/02/SRIA_final.pdf (July 2016)
- [2] 5G PPP CHARISMA website: <http://www.charisma5g.eu/>
- [3] M.C. Parker *et al.*, "CHARISMA: Converged Heterogeneous Advanced 5G Cloud-RAN Architecture for Intelligent and Secure Media Access", *EuCNC'16*, Athens, Greece, 29 June – 1 July 2016
- [4] M. Ulbricht *et al.* "Accelerated Processing Delay Optimization in Hierarchical Networks Using Lowcost Hardware", 2016 10th Int. Symp. Comm. Sys., Networks and Digital Signal Processing (CSNDSP)